

VIRTUAL OR2020 MEETINGS

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Programme: Open for all

Monday, June 1st

Virtual workshop: How repositories can contribute their FAIR share 1:00pm – 2:30pm UTC, [slides](#) and [recording](#)

Findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) data are an increasingly important aspect of open scholarship. Increasing the production and use of FAIR data requires a wide range of stakeholders across the research ecosystem to actively play their parts. FAIRsFAIR – Fostering Fair Data Practices in Europe – aims to supply practical solutions for applying the FAIR data principles throughout the research data life cycle, which can be included in the strategies that research organisations and implemented to enable a FAIR data culture.

This 90 minute virtual workshop will focus on the work FAIRsFAIR carries out in collaboration with repositories to enable them to play their role in helping to make and keep data FAIR over time. We will present an early draft of a transition support programme for repositories wishing to improve their capacity to support FAIR data production and use. Following an overview of the draft programme, attendees will participate in group discussions and activities to review and discuss the draft support programme, consider how it might be applied within their own repositories, and how they can support and promote relevant aspects of the programme within their institutions and the wider community.

Keynote, presentations and discussion: Equity and democratization of knowledge
3:00pm – 4:30pm UTC, [recording](#)

Welcome from Sarah L. Shreeves (Chair, Open Repositories Steering Committee) and Claire Knowles (Vice Chair, Open Repositories Steering Committee)

[Keynote “Reframing the conversation: applying the principles of diversity, equity and inclusion to scholarly communications”](#) – Kathleen Shearer, Executive Director, Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR) – and discussion

[Shareyourpaper.org](#) – Joseph McArthur, Open Access Button 4:00PM

[A pilot on usage data exchange between LA Referencia \(Latin America\) and OpenAIRE \(EU\) networks](#) – Washington Luís Ribeiro de Carvalho Segundo, Instituto Brasileiro de Informação em Ciência e Tecnologia 4:15PM

Tuesday, June 2nd

11:00am – 12:45pm UTC [recording](#)

[The National Academic Digital Repository of Ethiopia – Technical, policy and governance aspects](#) – Roberto Barbera, Department of Physics and Astronomy “E. Majorana” of the University of Catania 11:05AM

[Overcoming language barrier in open repositories: A case of Sokoine University of Agriculture](#) – Gilbert Mushi 11:20AM

[Skills needs assessment for South African open access repository practitioners](#) – Ansie van der Westhuizen, UNISA 11:35AM

The NREN and open repositories (an ORCID use case in South Africa) – Wesley Barry, TENET | Tertiary Education & Research Network of South Africa 11:50AM

[Documenting the ephemeral: Performance archive and the showcase repository](#) – Sanjin Muftic and Jayne Batzofin, The Reimagining Tragedy in Africa and the Global South (RETAGS) project at the University of Cape Town 12:05PM

[Evaluation of institutional digital repository contents by postgraduate students of some selected tertiary institutions in Nigeria](#) – Dr. Michael Esew, Kashim Ibrahim Library, Ahmadu Bello University, Okeoghene Mayowa-Adebara, National Open University of Nigeria, Ibadan Study Centre 12:20PM

[Institutional repository adoption among Nigerian private universities: Institutional factors and willingness to use](#) – Adetomiwa Basiru, Tekena Tamuno Library, Redeemer’s University 12:35PM

Working towards knowledge accessibility and visibility through collaboration efforts: the case of Botswana International University of Science and Technology (BIUST) library - Ayanda Lebele and Tuelo Ntlotlang, BIUST Library

Software day: Repository Rodeo and developer track ([recording](#)), posters 3:00pm – 5:30pm UTC

Repository Rodeo ([slides](#))

Dataverse: Danny Brooke, Harvard University

DSpace: Maureen Walsh, The Ohio State University

EPrints: John Salter, University of Leeds

Fedora: David Wilcox, LYRASIS

Haplo: Tom Renner, Haplo

Invenio: Lars Holm Nielsen, CERN

Islandora: Mark Jordan, Simon Fraser University

Samvera: Jon Dunn, Indiana University

Developer track:

Developing COrDa: The COmmunity Orcid Dashboard; The powerful chamber: an institutional overview of the ORCID registry – Adam Vials Moore, JISC 4:10PM

API driven applications with GraphQL; Building a modern repository UI with Elasticsearch, React and IIIF – Adam J. Arling, Northwestern University Libraries 4:20PM

Virtual posters session 4:30PM UTC <https://or2020.sun.ac.za/virtual-poster-session>

1. Abdulla, Mohamed Abdulla. Open Access and discovery of digital repository in Sudanese universities: Opportunities and challenges
2. Abu-Alam, Tamer S. Open Polar: Thematic harvesting of Polar region resources
3. Bruno, Riccardo. The Reproducibility and Reusability Platform
4. Carvalho-Segundo, Washington Luís. Discovering trending topics in open digital repositories
5. Eid, Sherine. A framework for a terminology management system in the Arab region

6. Ferreira, Tiago Martins da Costa. Brazilian DSpace community: The experience to unleash collaboration
7. Groneberg, Antje. Modifying, refining and developing new features for a Research Information System (RIS) at Helmut-Schmidt-University Hamburg
8. Kahsay, Kiflom Michael. Building an Open Access repository in Eritrea with limited resources. *(will not be presented virtually)*
9. Kotarski, Rachael. Shared repositories: Building a multi-tenancy repository service at the British Library
10. Maringanti, Harish. Feasibility of applying off-the-shelf Artificial Intelligence tools on digital library images collections
11. Mosterd, Tom. OAPEN Open Access Books Toolkit
12. Ndhlovu, Philip. Measuring the Impact of Institutional Repositories in selected Zimbabwean State Universities
13. Olivares, Cesar. A widely deployable and OpenAire-compatible DSpace usage data collector for LA Referencia
14. PIŠČANC, Jordan. UnityFVG – Regional Research Portal implementing OpenAIRE CRIS/Data/Literature Guidelines with DSpace-CRIS
15. Ramalho, Lucca de Farias. Methodology for building digital thematic libraries
16. Roux, Marié. Stellenbosch University's ORCID integration: The highs and the lows
17. Sanchez, Carolina. The experience of getting a “No Code” open repository
18. Sanchez, Carolina. Data mining, NLP and Machine Learning at the service of a scalable open repository *(will not be presented virtually)*
19. Shahadu, Sadik. Crafting an OER network in Ghana using IndieWeb building blocks
20. Stover, Sharon. Towards ethical data management, distribution, and use for artificial intelligence (AI) applications
21. Vials Moore, Adam. Evolving the PID Landscape

Wikidata virtual workshop 6:00pm – 8:00pm UTC, [recording](#)

Since Wikidata's launch in 2012 as an open, collaboratively edited knowledge base, it's held great promise for the library and scholarly communications community more broadly. Institutions and individual information professionals turned Wikidatans are using Wikidata to build a community-owned infrastructure for the bibliographic ecosystem, including open source tools that generate profiles of scholars, organizations, and publications. This workshop will introduce participants to Wikidata and its linked data infrastructure, including an overview of tools that facilitate data contribution and use. Participants will leave prepared to connect with existing Wikidata initiatives, and with entry points to launch their own. Facilitator: Wacha, Megan, CUNY

Wednesday, June 3rd

Virtual workshop: Co-designing policies, repository infrastructures and services and strengthening open science communities in Africa 11:00am – 2pm UTC

This LIBSENSE workshop co-organized by WACREN, UbuntuNet Alliance, ASREN, EIFL, COAR, AfricaConnect 3, OpenAIRE and GÉANT, will convene the African community of repository managers and other open access services and advocates and cover three topics: 1) Open Access, Open Science policies and repositories: what works and what doesn't; 2) repository infrastructure and services: how to build cohesiveness across layers of local, national and regional services; and 3) communities of practice: how to strengthen open science communities in Africa. African participants will share experiences, lessons learned and discuss how to best design effective Open Access and Research Data Management policies and how to progress their adoption and implementation. They will also co-design the guiding principles for institutional repositories to follow in order to build services on top of repositories and cohesiveness across local, national and regional repository services. And together we will develop a roadmap for strengthening open science communities in Africa. With breakout groups in Arabic, English, French and Portuguese. [Slides](#)

Current issues 3:00pm – 4:30pm UTC, [recording](#)

Panel: “Aligning repository networks to support international sharing of COVID-19 resources”, organized by COAR. This panel will present several national approaches to managing and sharing COVID-19 resources from around the world (Africa, Canada, Europe, Latin America, Asia), followed by a discussion about how we can work more closely across countries and regions to ensure that content can be integrated internationally. Participants: Kathleen Shearer – COAR, Paolo Manghi – OpenAIRE, Europe, Kazuhiro Hayashi – National Institution of Science and Technology Policy, Japan, Ansie Van de Wasthuizen – UNISA, South Africa, Cesar Olivares – CONCYTEC, Peru and LA Referencia, Latin America, Geoff Harder – Canadian Association of Research Libraries.

Organization identifiers and open repositories: ROR-ing together – Maria Gould, California Digital Library, University of California Office of the President 3:50PM

Research Data Management: a Stellenbosch University journey – Samuel Simango, Stellenbosch University Library 4:00PM

Towards Open Data Metrics: enabling data repositories to demonstrate reuse – Kristian Garza, DataCite 4:15PM

DSpace-CRIS 7: What is coming? – Susanna Mornati, 4Science 4:30PM

Thursday, June 4th 3:00pm – 4:30pm UTC, [recording](#)

Investing in Open Science infrastructure and repositories: How IOI and SCOSS can help – Vanessa Proudman, SPARC Europe 3:08PM

Shared repositories: building a multi-tenancy repository service at the British Library – Sara Gould, the British Library 3:20PM

A year long Ideas Challenge: The new beginning. An online social gathering to kick-off Ideas Challenge 2020-2021 – presentation and discussion with breakout sessions. For more information, please visit the Ideas Challenge page.

Thank you and closing

Programme Committee

Programme Co-Chairs

Iryna Kuchma, EIFL

Lazarus Matizirofa, University of Pretoria

Dr Daisy Selematsela, University of South Africa

Leila Serman, Montana State University

Members

Adam Field, Jisc

Wouter Klapwijk, Stellenbosch University

Liz Krznarich, ORCID

Harish Maringanti, Marriott Library, University of Utah

Michele Mennielli, LYRASIS

Andrew Mwesigwa, Makerere University Library

Tomasz Neugebauer, Concordia University

Kim Pham, University of Denver

Nancy Pontika, Open University and CORE

Marié Roux, Stellenbosch University Library

Alan Stiles, Open University

Abenet Yabowork, International Livestock Research Institute

Local Hosts

Ellen R. Tise and Mimi Seyffert-Wirth, [Stellenbosch University Library and Information Service](#)

OR 2020 Fellows

Several years ago the Open Repositories Steering Committee (ORSC) initiated a fellows program where we offer full scholarships to a handful of applicants after a review process. We had just selected a group of fellows for Open Repositories 2020 in Stellenbosch when the pandemic struck, and we had to pivot to a virtual program. So we wanted to be sure that the broader OR community is aware of the OR2020 Fellows. They are:

Adetomiwa Basiru, [Redeemer's University](#), Nigeria

Kiwanuka Luke Francis, [Makerere University](#) Library, Uganda

Ester Ernest Mnzava, [Sokoine University of Agriculture](#), Tanzania

Tuelo Ntlotlang, [Botswana International University of Science and Technology](#), Botswana

Kiflom Michael Kahsay, [Research and Documentation Centre](#), Eritrea

Djogbenou Sogodo Leon, [Media Library of French Institute in Benin](#), Benin

Congratulations to this group!

Website and Social Media

Website: <https://or2020.sun.ac.za>

Slides and recording: <https://zenodo.org/communities/openrepos>
(<https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=keywords:%22OR2020%22>)

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/OpenRepo2020>

Hashtag: [#openrepos2020](#)

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/ORConference>